

THE PROBLEMS ASSOCIATED WITH NEOLOGISMS IN THE PROCESS OF TRANSLATION

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Abstract: Translation of neologisms presents significant challenges due to the dynamic and innovative nature of language. Neologisms often emerge to describe new technologies, social phenomena, or cultural concepts, making their equivalents in target languages limited or non-existent. Translators face difficulties in preserving both the semantic meaning and stylistic nuances of these terms. Common strategies include calquing, borrowing, adaptation, and antonymic translation; however, each method has inherent limitations. Calquing may not always convey the full cultural context, while borrowing can disrupt the linguistic naturalness of the target language. Antonymic translation, though useful for explanation, often results in longer or less precise expressions. This study explores these challenges, providing examples from English and Uzbek, and emphasizes the importance of context, cultural awareness, and creative linguistic solutions in the effective translation of neologisms.

The word neologism is a Greek combination where “neo” means “new” and “logos” means “word.” The first time this word appeared in English was way back in 1772. People have been making up new words for centuries, but that’s when neologism was first recorded. Since then, it’s been used to describe all kinds of fresh, creative words people come up with. Neologism is used for words or phrases created in response to changes in our culture, society, or technology. Neologisms are essential for making language richer and showing how things are now in a world where language is constantly changing. They can be completely new words, changes to existing words, or new phrases that describe new ideas or events. New words like “selfie” and “binge-watch” commonly come from popular culture, technology, and social media. This shows how language changes to keep up with how people live. Learning about neologisms increases our language skills and uncovers how a community shares and reacts to creative and challenging events. This article from a Canadian certified translator will explore what neologism means, how it is used in language, and how it affects our

communication. A **neologism** is a recently created word, phrase, or a new usage of an existing term. According to Merriam-Webster, it refers to “a new word, usage, or expression,” while Britannica describes it as “a new word or a newly assigned meaning to an old one.” In short, it’s a fresh addition to a language. Neologisms can emerge from casual speech, internet culture, literature, or even unintentionally. Some become widely accepted—such as “blog” or “emoji”—whereas others disappear over time. Yet every neologism begins the same way: someone introduces a word in a way it hasn’t been used before.

The actuality of this theme is that neologisms are very important in our life, especially now, because we have a development of science and technology, the new courses in the field of literature, art and music etc. And there are a lot of new words created in different fields. All these mean that the actuality of this theme is very important. Sometimes people even don't know the meaning of some abbreviations because they are new. Indeed, sometimes with the abbreviations such as AIDS, the unabbreviated form may be so specialized that it is unknown to most people - a point not missed by the compilers of quiz games, who regularly catch people out with a well-known abbreviation and another types of neologisms. In studying the processes of lexical renewal in the English language, it becomes evident that its development is increasingly shifting toward creating new words using the language’s own internal resources. The following main methods of forming neologisms are identified:

1. affixation (prefixation and suffixation);
2. conversion as a morpho-syntactic method of word formation;
3. compounding

Affixal neologisms account for more than one-fifth of all new words. They are formed within conventional word-formation patterns; however, many already existing suffixes begin to acquire additional, new meaning. For example:

-able: *googlable* (something that can be found through search engines); *microwaveable* (suitable for cooking in a microwave oven).

-holic: *bookholic* (a person obsessed with books); *chocoholic* (obsessed with chocolate), *coffeeholic* (a person obsessed with coffee), *clotheholic* (obsessed with clothes), *shopaholic* (a compulsive shopper).

-ian: *facebookian* (a user of the social network Facebook).

-ic: *villagistic* (relating to a village).

-ism: *ageism* (discrimination based on age); *lookism* (bias against a person because of their appearance); *sexism* (sex-based discrimination); *masculinism* (advocacy of a dominant male role in society).

-ization: *dollarization; globalization.*

-land: *adland* (the advertising industry).

-ology: *boomerology* (the study of people born during the Baby Boom era); *peopleology* (the study of people).

-ous: *rainbowlicious* (bright, colorful, vibrant).

Prefixes also play an active role in word formation. The most common include:

cyber-: *cybercafé; cybercrime; cyberfraud; cybersickness.*

de-: *to deconflict* (to prevent a conflict); *to defriend* (to remove someone from a friend list on social networks).

dis-: *to disclude* (to exclude); *dispatriotism* (lack of patriotism).

Ways of translation neologisms:

Calquing, or **loan translation**, is a method of translating neologisms by **reproducing their internal structure and meaning literally** in the target language. Instead of borrowing the foreign word itself, the translator recreates it using the **morphological and lexical resources** of the target language. Literal translation of a single neologism. Example: *cybercrime* → “cyber + crime” (kiberjinoyat), *globalization* → “globe + -ization” → globallashuv

Descriptive way of translating neologisms is the most flexible method especially when it comes to translating literary. The word explained fully into target language to understand the context fully. Example: *cybercafe* (café equipped with internet resources)

Analogue in this process new words will create based on the neologisms' core meanings, example: *nonversation*-meaningless conversation

Antonymic translation- no direct equivalent exists in the target language. For example, new technological or social concepts may not have a single-word translation. **Meaning can be conveyed through the opposite.** The neologism is explained by negating its antonym. **A neutral or softer expression is needed.** Common in academic, social, or pedagogical texts.

Overall, translating neologisms remains a complex and demanding task due to their innovative and culture-specific nature. The challenges arise from the lack of direct equivalents, semantic nuances, and stylistic considerations in the target language. While strategies such as calquing, borrowing, adaptation, and antonymic translation provide useful tools, each approach has its limitations and must be applied thoughtfully. Successful translation of neologisms requires not only linguistic proficiency but also cultural awareness, creativity, and flexibility. By carefully selecting appropriate strategies and considering context, translators

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can effectively convey both the meaning and the originality of neologisms, contributing to the growth and enrichment of the target language.

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